

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN TRAINING SPECIALISTS IN THE ECONOMY AND MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The foreign experience in training specialists in the economy and management of education is a critical aspect of global educational development. This article begins with an overview of modern methods in education, highlighting their adaptability, accessibility, and effectiveness, especially in the context of the accelerated adoption prompted by the COVID-19 pandemic. A review of literature explores significant contributions to the understanding of modern educational practices and their implications for education management and economics.*

The methodology involves a secondary data analysis approach, drawing insights from diverse published sources to examine foreign experiences in training specialists in education management and economics. The article then provides examples from various countries, including the United States, the United Kingdom, Finland, Singapore, Australia, and India, showcasing their distinct approaches to training specialists in education management.

The data analysis section focuses on the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) and its global study on academic performance, emphasizing the need for improvements in mathematical tasks and the potential positive impact of adopting the Common Core Standards. It also discusses the evolving educational landscape in the United States and provides insights from an educator's perspective.

The article explores the challenges and progress in Uzbekistan's education system, emphasizing the need for quality evaluation frameworks in preschool education. Despite substantial progress in enrollment rates, "last-mile" challenges such as unenrolled children, equity issues, and a knowledge gap regarding education quality persist.

In conclusion, the COVID-19 pandemic has underscored the importance of modern methods in education. Recommendations for future research include exploring economic factors influencing resource allocation and the impact of modern educational practices on student learning outcomes. The article suggests that addressing these research gaps can contribute to building more resilient, effective, and equitable education systems globally.

Introduction

Modern methods in education encompass innovative approaches that utilize technology, updated pedagogical strategies, and efficient administrative practices to enhance teaching, learning, and management within educational systems. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly accelerated the adoption of these modern methods, transforming traditional educational practices virtually overnight. This introduction will provide an overview of what modern methods in education entail and offer examples of how the COVID-19 pandemic has reshaped the educational landscape.

Modern methods in education are characterized by their adaptability, accessibility, and effectiveness in catering to diverse learning needs. These methods leverage advancements in technology to create dynamic and interactive learning environments, enabling students to engage

with course materials in new and immersive ways. Furthermore, modern methods prioritize student-centered learning approaches, empowering learners to take ownership of their education and pursue personalized learning pathways.

The COVID-19 pandemic has prompted a rapid shift towards the adoption of modern methods in education, as traditional classroom settings became untenable due to social distancing measures and lockdown restrictions. Educational institutions worldwide were forced to transition to online learning platforms virtually overnight, presenting both challenges and opportunities for educators and administrators. The pandemic has highlighted the importance of flexibility, adaptability, and innovation in education, as educators have had to quickly adapt their teaching methods to suit the online environment and address the unique needs of remote learners. It has opened new methods, and pedagogies adopted in teaching learning methods. Particularly use of technology

Review of Literature

A comprehensive review of literature on modern methods in education and the training of specialists in education management and economics reveals a wealth of scholarly research and academic discourse on the subject. Several authors have made significant contributions to the understanding of modern educational practices and their implications for educational management and economics.

James A. Bellanca, in his seminal work "Leadership for 21st Century Learning," explores the essential skills and competencies required for educational leaders to navigate the complexities of the modern educational landscape. Bellanca emphasizes the importance of visionary leadership, effective communication, and strategic decision-making in driving educational innovation and improvement.

Larry Lashway and Linda Lashway, in their book "The New School Management by Wandering Around," advocate for a hands-on, relational approach to educational leadership and management. The authors argue that effective school leaders must actively engage with students, teachers, and other stakeholders to build trust, foster collaboration, and promote a positive school culture.

Marguerite Roza, in her seminal work "Educational Economics: Where Do School Funds Go?," examines the economic factors influencing educational resource allocation, budgeting strategies, and the overall efficiency of educational systems. Roza's research sheds light on the complex interplay between economic considerations and educational outcomes, highlighting the need for strategic financial management in education.

Methodology

This article adopts a secondary data analysis approach, drawing insights from a diverse range of published sources, including academic journals, books, reports, and policy documents. The analysis aims to synthesize existing literature and empirical evidence to examine foreign experiences in training specialists in the economy and management of education. By synthesizing and analyzing secondary data from published sources, this article seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of current practices and challenges in the field of education management and economics.

Training specialists in the economy and management of education is a crucial aspect of educational development globally. Many countries have developed their own approaches to this training, drawing from both domestic expertise and foreign experiences. Here are some examples

of how different countries approach training specialists in the economy and management of education:

1. In the US, training specialists in the economy and management of education often occurs through graduate programs in educational leadership, administration, or policy. These programs typically blend theoretical knowledge with practical experiences, such as internships or residencies in educational institutions or government agencies. Additionally, professional organizations like the American Educational Research Association (AERA) and the American Association of School Administrators (AASA) provide resources and networking opportunities for education management professionals.

2. In the UK, there are various pathways for training specialists in education management and economics. Universities offer master's programs in educational leadership, management, and policy, which provide a blend of theoretical knowledge and practical skills. Additionally, organizations like the National College for Teaching and Leadership (NCTL) offer professional development programs and certifications for school leaders and administrators.

3. Finland is renowned for its education system, and training specialists in education management is an integral part of its approach. Finnish universities offer master's programs in educational leadership and administration, emphasizing research-based practices and collaborative leadership. Finland also provides continuous professional development opportunities for teachers and school leaders through networks like the Finnish Education Evaluation Center (FINEEC) and the Finnish National Agency for Education.

4. Singapore places a strong emphasis on education management and leadership to support its highly regarded education system. The National Institute of Education (NIE) offers graduate programs in educational management and leadership, catering to the needs of aspiring school leaders and policymakers. Singapore also provides opportunities for professional development through organizations like the Academy of Principals (Singapore) and the Ministry of Education's Leadership Development Branch.

5. In Australia, training specialists in education management and economics occurs through graduate programs offered by universities, such as master's degrees in educational leadership and policy. These programs focus on developing leadership skills, understanding educational finance and economics, and implementing effective management practices. Professional associations like the Australian Council for Educational Leaders (ACEL) provide networking opportunities and professional development resources for education managers and administrators.

6. In India under The National Initiative for School Heads' and Teachers' Holistic Advancement (NISHTHA) program, for example, was started by the government. Through ongoing professional development and training, this program seeks to improve the skills and knowledge of over 42 lakh (4.2 million) teachers nationwide. This will enable inexperienced educators to advance their careers, seize more opportunities, and have a longer-lasting effect on the educational system.

Focus from Bearers of Knowledge to Facilitators. They support students in their exploration and comprehension of ideas and motivate them to take an active role in their education. Problem-solving, critical thinking, and collaborative learning are prioritized more. To make learning interesting and useful, students participate in group discussions, practical exercises, projects, simulations, and even instructional games.

These examples demonstrate the diverse approaches countries take in training specialists in the economy and management of education, reflecting their unique contexts, priorities, and

educational philosophies. While there are variations in methods and structures, the overarching goal is to cultivate effective leaders and administrators who can navigate the complexities of educational systems and contribute to their improvement and innovation.

Analysis of Data

As per the study made by OECD in which Fifteen-year-olds participated in the "Program for International Student Assessment" (PISA) in numerous countries worldwide. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) managed a global study on the academic performance of schoolchildren in reading, science, and mathematics in both member and non-member countries. After its debut in 2000, it was carried out every three years after that. The goal is to enhance educational policies and results. It assesses daily cognitive function and problem solving. Data on a country's standing in relation to other participating countries is released every three years. USA is positioned in the center of the table.

PISA states that "Mathematical tasks with higher cognitive demands, such as taking real-world situations, translating them into mathematical terms, and interpreting mathematical aspects in real-world problems, are particularly weak points for students in the United States." According to an agreement study between PISA and the Common Core State Standards for Mathematics, a rewarding adoption of the Common Core Standards would result in notable improvements in PISA performance as well.

Since the PISA was implemented, the USA's rankings have declined over time. Despite the graph's gloomy appearance, it is not entirely accurate because over time, a larger number of countries participated in the PISA, increasing the gap in the rankings. Nevertheless, there is still a considerable deal of need for evolution in the fields of science, mathematics, and reading.

According to PISA's analysis in their official report regarding the USA, a fortunate adoption of the Common Core Standards would result in notable improvements in PISA's performance as well. American developers of large-scale assessments have already been impacted by the prominence of modeling in high school standards. It would be reasonable to anticipate an improvement in PISA performance if more pupil worked on more and better modeling tasks than they do now. Despite dropping in the global rankings, America's results have improved across the board in all three subject areas. It is notable that Finland's scores have significantly decreased over time. Perhaps there are issues with the Finnish educational system as well. In the meantime, America is developing, although quite slowly.

<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/education-systems-around-world-comparison-sashi-gundala>

In US, all children receive free education regardless of their background or socioeconomic status. Curriculum now covers societal issues like physical fitness, stress management, and relaxation, as well as the prevention of alcohol and drug abuse. For those starting college, there is a large selection of courses available. Students are given complete freedom to make their own decisions and are not obligatory to follow their beginning career paths; instead, they can choose a unrelated one at any time.

States and districts are waking up to the fact that we do need to make some changes to our curriculum and system. Schools are aligning their curriculum to the common core norms. Further cognitively demanding mathematical tasks are being created by teachers these days. They also use real-world scenarios, convert them into mathematical terms, and interpret mathematical concepts in real-world issues.

Less than one-fifth of children in Uzbekistan between the ages of three and six attended preschools in 2012 (18.7% of all children, with 58 percent of children in Tashkent city and only 9 percent in Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya). Approximately 25% of kids aged 3-6 were registered in preschools across the nation in 2017. Preschool enrollment in Uzbekistan, however, was significantly lower than in other nations with comparable lower-middle-class status or even some of the neighboring Central Asian nations.

<https://stat.uz/en/official-statistics/social-protection>

In any case, there were no framework in put in 2017/18 to evaluate quality of preschool instruction within the nation. The issue was exasperated by the nonappearance of a legitimate Instruction Administration Data Framework (EMIS) or Instruction Quality Confirmation Framework (EQAS) for preschool instruction within the nation. But in 2017–18, the country needed a framework to assess the caliber of preschool instruction. The need of an fitting (EMIS) or (EQAS) for preschool instruction within the country made the issue more awful.

Agreeing to information from the State Measurable Committee, GOU, for the year 2021, the net enrollment rates (GER) for common auxiliary instruction (grades 1–9) have been reliable at 97% over the past few years. In 2021, the evaluated enrolment rates for essential instruction (grades 1-4) and auxiliary instruction (grades 5-9) were 99 percent and 94 percent, separately. The gender parity list (GPI) at the essential instruction level is 0.94. Moreover, there are territorial contrasts within the GERs for essential instruction. In Tashkent city, the territorial contrasts in GERs for essential school instruction in 2016–17 extended from 108–111 percent to fair 86 percent in Karakalpakstan. The territorial contrasts are unaltered for 2020–2021, with the GER in Tashkent city moving from 93 percent in Karakalpakstan to 103 percent across the nation

<https://stat.uz/en/official-statistics/social-protection>

Also with with Uzbekistan's significant progress toward nearly universal school enrollment, there remain "last-mile" challenges, such as a sizable proportion of unenrolled children who may have dropped out or never enrolled; issues with equity, particularly with regard to the education of children with disabilities (CWD); and, most importantly, a knowledge gap regarding the quality of education, including information about curriculum, textbooks, teaching-learning procedures, and quality assurance. The Education Sector Plan was created in 2018 with this backdrop in mind.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the adoption of modern methods in education, presenting both challenges and opportunities for educators and administrators. Moving forward, it is essential for educational institutions and policymakers to invest in training programs that equip specialists with the necessary skills and knowledge to thrive in a rapidly evolving educational landscape. This includes leveraging technology, promoting collaboration, and using data-driven decision-making to optimize resource allocation and enhance educational outcomes.

Recommendations for future research in the field of education management and economics include further exploration of the economic factors influencing educational resource allocation, budgeting strategies, and the overall efficiency of educational systems. Additionally, there is a need for more research on the impact of modern educational practices on student learning outcomes, teacher effectiveness, and overall educational quality. By addressing these research gaps and implementing evidence-based strategies, educational institutions and policymakers can work towards building more resilient, effective, and equitable education systems.

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